

CO-OPTResilient Coasts:
Optimising Co-Benefit Solutions

BUILDING A SHARED PERSPECTIVE ON HESKETH OUT MARSH THROUGH CO- PRODUCTION

WORKSHOP REPORT

6 June 2024

Hesketh Bank Community Centre

Project funded by

About Co-opt project

[Resilient Coasts: Optimising Co-Benefit Solutions \(Co-Opt\)](#) is a research collaboration between the National Oceanographic Centre, Cranfield University, the University of Liverpool and the University of St Andrews that focuses on scalable and adaptive approaches to support coastal and shoreline management in partnership with regional, national, and local decision-makers. The project has been funded by the Natural Environment Research Council (NERC)-Economic and Social Research Council (ESRC) [Sustainable Management of UK Marine Resources Programme](#).

Summary

This report summarises the process and outputs of a workshop organised and funded via the Co-Opt research project and hosted by Hesketh Bank Community Centre on the 6th of June 2024. The workshop brought together participants who are interested and/or affected by the Hesketh Out Marsh managed realignment, including representatives of government agencies, local government, farmers and nature conservation charities.

The objective of the workshop and of this report is **to build a shared understanding** of the current challenges at Hesketh Out Marsh and the surrounding area and **outline the steps required** to address them. This workshop served as a starting point for a collaborative and innovative approach to decision-making for this area. Diverse, and sometimes contrasting, views exist about the success and effectiveness of this managed realignment scheme. A **participatory approach** (co-production) was therefore adopted to foster a shared understanding of the social-ecological challenges in the area. This participatory process, which values equal contributions from all participants, highlights the importance of **co-creation in decision-making and coastal management**.

This report seeks to gather and present the diverse perspectives of the participants. An initial draft was prepared and shared with participants for their feedback, which was subsequently collected and incorporated into the final version. We made every effort to include all the feedback received and believe that we have addressed the most significant points.

The main issues related to Hesketh Out Marsh were highlighted to be **fragmented responsibilities in terms of maintenance and the siltation of outfalls**. The area is under pressure due to constraints on the drainage system and a lack of funding. Participants identified many potential responses and preparatory measures, highlighting **improved strategic planning, public engagement and stakeholder collaboration** as some of the essential future actions.

This report focuses on Hesketh Out Marsh but is designed to function as a standalone document for wide distribution. It also serves as an example of a participatory process that can be adapted for local decision-making in other contexts.

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ACKNOWLEDGMENTS: WE WOULD LIKE TO EXPRESS OUR GRATITUDE TO ALL THE PARTICIPANTS OF THIS STUDY, WHOSE WILLINGNESS TO SHARE THEIR EXPERIENCES CREATED THE DEPTH AND RICHNESS OF THIS RESEARCH. WE ALSO WANT TO THANK THE HESKETH BANK COMMUNITY CENTRE THAT HOSTED OUR WORKSHOP. WE WOULD LIKE TO EXTEND OUR GRATITUDE TO TIM STOJANOVIC FOR HIS VALUABLE FINAL COMMENTS, WHICH CONTRIBUTED TO THE COMPLETION OF THIS REPORT.

CITATION: MESCHINI, M. & APINE, E. (2025). BUILDING A SHARED PERSPECTIVE ON HESKETH OUT MARSH THROUGH CO-PRODUCTION. DOI: 10.5281/ZENODO.14833036

Introduction

Coastal communities both benefit from and are threatened by the sea. Extreme events such as storms already have a large impact on the coast, with damages due to coastal flooding, erosion, and other coastal hazards. Coastal flooding was one of the highest hazards on the UK government's risk register in 2017. About 2.8 million properties are at risk of flooding from rivers and the sea in England alone*. Coastal hazards will be increasing over the next century primarily driven by unavoidable sea level rise. There is a need to manage the coast to ensure the resilience of coastal communities to extreme events. Simultaneously, the UK is committed to reaching net zero carbon emissions by 2050 and achieving national and international biodiversity goals such as biodiversity net gain (BNG) in England and Kunming-Montreal Global Biodiversity Framework 2030 Targets.

One potential solution is managed realignment, which involves breaching primary coastal defences to create intertidal habitats such as saltmarshes. These habitats provide dual benefits: they contribute to biodiversity goals while offering natural flood protection. An example is the Hesketh Out Marsh managed realignment scheme, designed to compensate for habitat loss in Morecambe Bay and support the objectives of the National and Lancashire Biodiversity Action Plans. While the multiple benefits of managed realignment, such as biodiversity enhancement and habitat creation, are well-recognised, concerns have emerged regarding local flooding issues. In fact, residents and landowners, through activities under the CoOpt project, have reported surface water flooding as a result of multiple and interacting factors such as intense rainfall events, soil compaction, development pressures, maintenance of drainage systems, and land use change.

Scope of the workshop

In order to create a shared understanding and knowledge of the current situation in Hesketh Out Marsh and its surrounding area, the Co-Opt project organised a workshop at the Hesketh Bank Community Centre on June 6, 2024. The workshop brought together participants from various groups affected by or interested in the Hesketh Out Marsh managed realignment site to discuss issues from their diverse perspectives.

The objectives of the workshop were:

- to share the information collected and developed by the project team and gather participants' opinions and views on Hesketh Out Marsh;
- to explore the impacts of various pressures (e.g., changes in local development, agricultural land conversion to saltmarshes) and discuss measures to address them using the Drivers-Pressure-State-Impact-Responses (DPSIR+) framework;
- to develop a shared understanding of Hesketh Out Marsh as part of the broader social-ecological system, including its challenges and potential future directions.

* [Flood and coastal erosion risk management report: 1 April 2022 to 31 March 2023. Environment Agency.](#)

Background

Hesketh Out Marsh, located along the Ribble Estuary in North-West England near Hesketh Bank, is a Royal Society for the Protection of Birds (RSPB) Nature Reserve and part of the wider Ribble Estuary National Nature Reserve. The saltmarsh and intertidal habitats recreated via managed realignment — allowing tidal waters to enter the reclaimed land — provide an important habitat for birds and other animals in the estuary.

The Ribble Estuary is included in the Northwest England North Wales Shoreline Management Plan (SMP2), which outlines strategies for coastal flood and erosion control in the short, medium and long term. Historically, the marshland in Hesketh Out Marsh was reclaimed for agriculture in the 1980s, but its potential for managed realignment was identified as a strategic flood defence option before 2000. With regards to flood protection, the West Lancashire Borough Council is the coastal protection authority and the Lancashire County Council acts as a lead local flood authority for the area.

Hesketh Out Marsh West

Hesketh Out Marsh West (blue area on the left side of Figure 1) was selected for managed realignment due to its recent reclamation, strategic elevation, and importance as a habitat for wintering wildfowl. RSPB negotiated with the landowners to acquire the site and manage it as a nature reserve, supported by funding from the Environment Agency and Lancaster City Council.

In 2006, the managed realignment of Hesketh Out Marsh West began through a collaboration between the RSPB, the Environment Agency, and Lancaster City Council. The project aimed to restore the former salt marsh ecosystem, which included creeks and lagoons that existed before the land was reclaimed for agriculture. This involved removing parts of an embankment built in the 1980s to allow tidal waters back into the area. By 2008, 168 hectares of salt marsh habitat were restored, enhancing biodiversity and serving as a natural flood defence, dissipating tidal energy.

Hesketh Out Marsh East

The second phase of the project focused on **Hesketh Out Marsh East** (red area on the right side of Figure 1), began in 2014 and completed in 2017. With funding from various sources, including a £1 million grant from WREN’s Biodiversity Action Fund, the RSPB acquired additional land for realignment. The project involved breaching the outer flood bank to restore more salt marsh habitat.

The total cost of this phase was £7.2 million, covering land acquisition, project management, and visitor facilities. The restoration of the eastern section brought the total restored area to 322 hectares, making it one of the largest managed realignment projects in the UK. See Figure 2 below for a summary of the main changes that have occurred at this site from the 1970s to the present.

Figure 1. Map showing Hesketh Out Marsh area. Based upon Land Cover Map 2019 © UKCEH 2020. Contains Ordnance Survey data © Crown Copyright 2007, Licence number 100017572. Map created with Digimap.

Hesketh Out Marsh today

Hesketh Out Marsh is now a vital habitat for various bird species, including pink-footed geese, wigeons, redshanks, and lapwings, attracting wildlife enthusiasts and conservationists. Light grazing by cattle is used to maintain the salt marsh vegetation, which helps preserve the habitat for these species. The site also provides flood protection for 143 residential properties and three commercial buildings from potential 1-in-200-year flood events.*

The Hesketh Out Marsh realignment project has, overall, been successful in restoring intertidal habitat and enhancing biodiversity. However, farmers, growers, landowners and residents have expressed concerns about flood resilience, as water tends to remain at elevated levels in ditches for extended periods. This prolonged retention inhibits field drainage, as water cannot flow effectively through outfalls due to siltation. Yet, many other low-lying communities in the North West, which have not experienced managed realignment projects in the area, are facing similar surface water drainage concerns. This suggests that it is challenging to pinpoint the specific impacts of managed realignment as multiple factors such as increased rainfall events, soil compaction and development pressures, contribute to increased surface water flood risk at a local level.

* Fellows, G. & Shirres, R. (2017). Case study 49. Hesketh Out Marsh Managed Realignment.

CHANGES TO HESKETH OUT MARSH

Figure 2. Changes that have occurred at this site from the 1970s to the present. Figures created by Amani Becker for this report.

Activities during the workshop

To explore how coastal management is perceived in Hesketh Bank and the key issues and causes of them, all relevant risk management authorities, local councillors, and other organisations were invited to the workshop. The participants were selected purposively to include various interest groups, including, decision-makers and landowners affected by flooding (see Table A1). During the day, participants were invited to use a modified Drivers-Pressures-State-Impacts-Responses (DPSIR) framework (see Table 1 below for a definition of these components). This framework is widely used to assess and manage environmental problems, including for coastal and marine environments. In this workshop, participants were also asked to consider the current “bigger picture” which influences the local situation (Worldview) and how the issues are perceived by the local community and risk management authorities (Social Acceptance). Due to these additions, we use the term DPSIR+ framework (see Figure 3 for an example of the structure of DPSIR+ framework). The workshop followed three main steps.

Figure 3. Example of the structure of the DPSIR+ framework that was used during the workshop.

Step 1

Participants were paired with one Co-Opt project researcher to develop their groups’ DPSIR+ frameworks based on their expertise and point of view. Participants were given an example developed by the facilitators of the session with cut-out entries that could be added if needed. Yet participants were also encouraged to add their own entries that were not considered in the example using post-it notes.

After developing their group’s DPSIR + frameworks, participants were asked to move the entries they thought were more relevant from their groups’ framework to the final shared framework.

Step 2

Step 3

Finally, each group was given an opportunity to elaborate and comment on their contributions to the shared framework.

Table 1. Definitions of the components taken into consideration in the DPSIR+ framework during the workshop in Hesketh Bank.

Drivers	are related to sectorial trends and policy drivers such as population growth, and net zero policies
Activities	are the human actions to address the drivers
Pressures	are mechanisms or human activities that are directly and negatively affecting the environment
State	(state change) is the observable change in the natural environment as a consequence of the pressures
Impacts	are related to the change in the state of the natural system impacting both the natural and human systems
Possible/potential responses	are the human actions (as measures) to respond to the drivers and pressures that caused the state change
Preparatory measures (preparation)	are practical actions to minimise the impacts of future activities and pressures
Social Acceptance	refers to the values and perceptions local community holds at the time of the activities
Worldview	is the set of values and the outlook which informs how people see the issue, for this framework it's related to global issues and global policies where these values are reflected

Results

The workshop was attended by ten individuals, including representatives from landowners, the Parish of Hesketh with Beconsall, West Lancashire Borough Council, the Environment Agency, Natural England, Our Future Coast, and the Royal Society for the Protection of Birds. Additionally, nine participants from the CoOpt project took part in the exercise.

Figure 4 illustrates the DPSIR+ frameworks created by the nine small groups during the workshop, while Figure 5 presents the shared DPSIR+ framework, which participants developed by integrating components identified in their group frameworks.

In the following pages, we summarise the key outcomes of the workshop, organised into common themes across different groups (page 12), key differences between groups (page 13), and reflections on the shared framework (page 14).

Figure 4. Photos of the group’s DPSIR+ frameworks developed during the workshop. Text is not readable because the scope of this image is to show visual differences in how the framework was developed among different groups.

Figure 5. Photo of the shared DPSIR+ framework developed by all groups together. Text is not readable because the scope of this image is just to visualise the shared framework.

1 COMMON THEMES among all group frameworks (see Table A2 for details)

SOCIAL ACCEPTANCE

Participants agreed that there are changing attitudes and values that influence Social Acceptance and there is an observable decrease in trust in risk management authorities.

WORLDVIEW

Participants highlighted that the Worldview is dominated by climate change and biodiversity crises, net zero and net gain policies and carbon credits for carbon sequestration, as well as the housing crisis.

DRIVERS

The main Drivers (sectorial trends) were agreed to be the housing crisis, house development, net gain and net zero policies, carbon credits, RSPB overall strategy/goal, post Brexit and Covid extremely challenging economic environment for the UK, climate change and biodiversity crises.

ACTIVITIES

The Activities to address the various drivers in Hesketh Bank were identified to be house development near the Douglas River, carbon issues and interest in carbon sequestration, taking samples to measure carbon sequestration in Hesketh Out Marsh, management and maintenance of the realigned site, main watercourses and outfalls.

RESPONSES

Among the responses, participants identified the need to switch from a sector/field-based approach to a system-based approach and that the management of managed realignment requires a holistic and long-term approach.

PRESSURE

The main Pressure in the area was almost unanimously agreed to be the increased pressure on the drainage system due to the housing development that leads to overflow/overcapacity in the system.

IMPACT

The state leads to Impacts such as flooding of farmlands, wildlife disturbance, increased flood experience and managed realignment not being perceived as effective in the current state.

STATE

Overall, almost all groups agree that the observable change (State) of Hesketh Out Marsh is the siltation of outfalls. Additionally, they recognise that responsibilities regarding flood risk management and Hesketh Out Marsh are fragmented and not always clear.

2 MAIN DIFFERENCES between all group's frameworks (see Table A3 for details)

The individual group's DPSIR+ frameworks largely reflected the perceptions and lived experiences of the participants.

In their DPSIR+ frameworks, farmers, growers and landowners emphasised the significance of the high-quality agricultural land in the region and its vital role in contributing to food production and food security. As **drivers**, they identified supermarket pricing, low-cost food, and the reduction in workforce post-Brexit as key factors. The main **pressure** they identified is the lack of maintenance of main rivers, watercourses and outfalls. Additionally, changes in the **state**, beyond the siltation of outfalls, were associated with negative **impacts** on food production and food security, a decline in farming, and the degradation of prime agricultural soil.

Concurrently, risk management authorities pointed to political motivations, complex governance structures, and funding mechanisms as key influences on the **state** of the system. Among the identified **impacts**, these representatives cited a decline in public trust in risk management efforts.

Each group proposed various detailed **responses and preparatory measures**. Landowners and farmers, for instance, advocated for recognition of the importance of farmland for regional and national food security, which would prioritise the area for flood protection. They also expressed a desire for increased investment in local flood protection schemes and wastewater treatment initiatives.

Other responses and preparatory measures centred on improved governance, greater accountability, enhanced collaboration among stakeholders, better public engagement, and increased funding.

In terms of **social acceptance**, one group highlighted the existence of misperceptions regarding nature-based solutions (e.g., their flood protection efficiency and the time required for establishment). Additionally, concerns were raised about the community's reluctance to engage, citing negative past experiences as a contributing factor.

The themes related to **Worldview** were consistent across groups, though one group specifically highlighted a lack of funding. It was further acknowledged that geopolitical priorities and political dynamics could influence coastal systems. Lastly, there was a consensus that the current funding schemes and planning processes do not effectively support the implementation of nature-based solutions. There is also a desire to see a shift towards a Worldview that meaningfully involves communities in decision-making processes.

3 SHARED FRAMEWORK of all participants (see Table A4 for details)

SOCIAL ACCEPTANCE

Participants placed **six** entries under Social Acceptance. Among them, one group highlighted that terms like "Nature-based solutions" are not well known by much of the public and that there is a low level of trust.

DRIVERS

Drivers consisted of **seventeen** entries, such as increasing extreme events and rainfall, cheap food, government policy, sea level rise, and politics.

WORLDVIEW

The Worldview consisted of **nine** entries that spanned from global concerns such as climate change, biodiversity crisis and geopolitics to national, such as food import and housing policies. This also included a more local worldview of managed realignment as an ineffective scheme in its current state.

ACTIVITIES

Nine activities address the drivers on a local scale. For example, management and maintenance of the realigned site, outfalls, main rivers and watercourses, and getting people on board through engagement.

PRESSURE

Pressures consisted of **five** entries that were mainly about lack of funding, increased pressure on drainage systems and wildlife disturbance.

STATE

The State was the second largest component with **twenty** themes added by the groups. The shared loop clearly acknowledged the siltation of outfalls to be a major problem of this coastal system as already indicated by the individual frameworks. Other issues were sewage discharge, increased flood experience, lack of maintenance of the realigned site, outfalls, main rivers and watercourses, and impact on food security. There was also a notion that sea-level rise is not perceived as a problem in Northwest England.

PREPARATORY MEASURES

The Preparation Measures had the most suggestions – **twenty-three** entries. They mainly highlighted the need to raise coastal flood management higher up in the policy agenda, improve governance and strategic planning, and invest in flood prevention and management. A major topic was also improving public engagement and cooperation between all interested parties, for example, giving more stewardship to the communities. Other shared preparatory measures included testing and trialling new coastal risk management approaches, increasing practitioners' expertise on nature-based solutions and deliberative processes, and making knowledge and evidence accessible.

RESPONSES

The **eleven** shared Responses were mainly concerned with transforming the governance and funding system. Furthermore, the proposed Responses recognised the role of farmers in flood risk management but called for incentives and support to undertake regenerative farming and farming with nature practices.

IMPACT

The **nine** Impacts caused by the State change were associated with flooding of farmlands, surface water flooding and competing interests.

Participant observations

This report aims to fairly represent the diverse perspectives of all participants, recognising that, at times, opinions differed significantly. Rather than trying to align the report with any particular viewpoint, we chose to include all the observations received during the review process when the report was shared with participants. We believe that all perspectives are equally important to consider and highlight.

- “...there will be **multiple factors affecting surface water flooding** locally. As mentioned in the workshop many other communities in the Northwest are experiencing similar surface water drainage concerns which have not experienced managed realignment projects in the area. More intense rainfall events, soil compaction, development pressures, maintenance of road and land drainage systems all contribute to this issue too. It would be good to acknowledge that we can’t accurately separate out the proportion that these various pressures contribute to surface water flood risk at a local scale and it will vary with different flood events.” (Regulators representative).
- “It is important to recognise that in **low-lying, flat areas** such as this, where water is not mechanically pumped, effective drainage to the sea is essential” (Landowners, farmers and growers representative).
- “It was disappointing the lack of **local farming & land owner representatives** at the event and very worrying that no one from the Lead Local Flood Authority - Lancashire County Council attended” (Landowners, farmers and growers representative).
- “Reference is made to the preservation of **wildlife** on the shore-side of the embankment. This may be the case on the out marsh and mud flats. It makes no mention of the destruction of wildlife, rabbits, hares other mammals, crustaceans and aquatic life created by the flooding of land and the increasing level of Ochre in the New Bank Drain on the inland side” (Landowners, farmers and growers representative).
- “It mentions the **embankment flood protection** to 143 occupants and 3 commercial properties etc. This was a statement made by the authorities concerned when applying for planning permission before realignment. However, while only two houses at 5mAOD have been flooded since and the now occupiers deceased, most of the other 141 properties left lie constantly at saturation point at foundation level. When previously the land drained freely and nothing flooded between 1967 and 2015” (Landowners, farmers and growers representative).
- “**Attendance unintentionally leaned towards the academics and authorities** with a total of 9 participants overall. Only 3 locals attended consisting of 2 Landowners (from information received by chance) 1 Parish councillor. Why did it happen like this? I personally think the reason for this was the lack of appropriately circulated information in the first place to the local people and stakeholders concerned ... I received it second-hand from a parish councillor, otherwise I clearly would not have known about it. If the information was sent out to the guest houses in the coastal resorts they may very well welcome it, but the flooding of this land since in this small section alone has cost the local farming community on Hesketh Marsh £2.5million in 2020 and we have been flooded and lost crops each year since then” (Landowners, farmers and growers representative).

Feedback received

After the workshop, we sent a feedback survey to participants to gather their thoughts on the process. Here, we highlight key points to help future activities build on what worked, what didn't, and the comments received.

All respondents (4 out of 4) stated that the workshop discussions enabled them to consider new perspectives, with comments such as:

“Understanding how other influences outside of my own work remit (food security, housing need, etc.) was really beneficial in helping to shape my thinking about future engagement needs for other sites along the estuary.”

“It helped me to understand better the various perspectives of the different stakeholders in the workshop.”

“The workshop gave me some hope that a better understanding of the various perspectives of the different stakeholders could lead to improved approaches to solving the problems that this area faces.”

Adjectives used by participants to describe the workshop. The bigger it is more time it was mentioned.

What did you like about the workshop?

- Down to earth and friendly discussion.
- It was very engaging and lots of varied topics of conversation.
- Interesting to listen to the updates on the various aspects of the project.
- The chance to put across our perspective of the problems we face and the reasons for some of these problems. Local knowledge is fundamental to finding and delivering solutions.

What did you not like about the workshop?

- More local people could have been invited/attended.
- Not enough time to fully address such a big topic.

What could we improve/ do better? (thinking about the whole process)

- It's not all about the implications of rising seas affecting the coastline. Each of the sectors should be given the opportunity to voice their concerns with a presentation about the pros and cons. Example sectors: 1 Scientist view, 2 Environment Agency objectives, 3 RSPB benefits plus and minus, 4 Natural England objectives, 5 Local Council view, 6 Farming community whose coastal land is affected.
- More local people could have been invited/attended.

Conclusions

This report aims to promote a shared understanding of the current challenges of Hesketh Out Marsh and to generate ideas for addressing its challenges. While it does not fully represent the perspectives of the entire community and local authorities due to limited participation, it serves as a foundation for a more inclusive and innovative approach to decision-making. By incorporating diverse perspectives and expertise, decisions can become more effective and holistic.

This report is based on the workshop held in a neutral academic setting, which brought together stakeholders including landowners, decision-makers, local councils, and the RSPB for constructive discussions. Participants shared their perspectives, reflected on past decisions, and addressed ongoing challenges. This open dialogue clarified key concerns and fostered mutual understanding among participants.

The workshop highlighted several key themes shaping the current situation in Hesketh Out Marsh.

- **Drivers of change** include the RSPB’s overarching goals and strategies, alongside broader issues such as the housing crisis and related development pressures.
- These local factors are further influenced by **global policies**, including commitments to net gain, net zero, and carbon credits, and global challenges such as climate change and biodiversity crisis.
- Locally, it is essential to **rebuild trust** in risk management authorities and explore shifting community values and attitudes. A comprehensive understanding of these factors will be vital in developing effective, inclusive strategies for Hesketh Out Marsh’s future.
- Participants identified **critical activities** needed in the area, such as the management and maintenance of the realigned site, outfalls, main rivers, and watercourses. Housing development has increased pressure on the drainage system, causing overcapacity and overflow issues. A significant concern raised was the siltation of outfalls and the fragmented, often unclear allocation of responsibilities for addressing these challenges.
- The current state of the area has led to **tangible impacts**, such as farmland flooding near the realigned site.
- To address these issues, participants emphasised the need for a **strategic and holistic approach** that recognises the system’s complexity and accommodates its diverse uses and users. This approach should guide planning, flood management, and conservation efforts, marking a shift from sector-based solutions to a system-based perspective.
- **Inadequate funding** for maintenance remains a persistent issue, hindering long-term planning for areas like Hesketh Out Marsh.
- **Public engagement** in projects and flood schemes has increasingly become a core element of early planning. When Hesketh Out Marsh began as a partnership project in 2003, engagement was more traditional, relying on one-off event in village halls and compiling feedback into a Communications Plan, leaving the community feeling unheard.

We hope this report serves as a standalone document, suitable for dissemination, and as an example of how participatory processes can be integrated into local decision-making. By engaging stakeholders early and effectively, future projects can build on this foundation, advancing collaboration and innovation to address challenges like those faced at Hesketh Out Marsh.

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APPENDIX

Table A1. List of organisations who took part into the CoOpt workshop in Hesketh Bank.

Cranfield University

Environment Agency

Landowner/farmer/business owner

National Oceanography Centre

Natural England

Our Future Coast project

Royal Society for the Protection of Birds

The Parish of Hesketh with Beconsall

University of Liverpool

University of St Andrews

West Lancashire Borough Council

Table A2. Common themes within groups for each component. The numbers in brackets indicate the number of the group(s) that reported the entry. To analyse the DPSIR framework, we grouped similar entries into themes.

Social Acceptance	Drivers	Activities	Pressures	State	Impact	Responses	Preparatory Measures	Worldview
changing values and attitudes (2, 7, 8,9)	carbon issues and interest on carbon sequestration (5, 8)	carbon issues and interest on carbon sequestration (3, 7)	flooding of farmlands (6, 7)	decrease in trust in risk management authorities (2, 8)	flooding of farmlands (1, 2, 3, 4, 5,9)	increase of trust and procedural justice (5, 7, 9)	management of the marine environment therefore requires a holistic approach that recognises the complexity of the system and accommodates the diverse range of uses and users (5, 8)	carbon issues and interest on carbon sequestration (2, 4, 5, 8, 9)
decrease in trust in risk management authorities (5, 7, 9)	climate change and biodiversity crises (5, 8, 9)	house development near the Douglas River (2, 6, 9)	flooding risk management is continuing issue in the UK taking quite a lot of resources (EA level of resources needed compared to 10 years earlier) (6, 7)	house development near the Douglas River (3, 5)	increased flood experience (1, 4, 5)	management and maintenance of the realigned site, gutters, and outfalls (1, 2, 7)		climate change and biodiversity crises (1, 4, 5, 7, 8, 9)
managed realignment is not perceived as an efficient flood risk management scheme in the current status (7, 9)	house development (2, 5, 6, 9)	management and maintenance of the realigned site, outfalls, main rivers and watercourses (3, 5, 8, 9)	increased pressure on the drainage system due to the housing development that leads to overflow/overcapacity in the system (1, 2, 3, 4, 6, 7, 8, 9)	increased flood experience (2, 3, 6)	managed realignment is not perceived as an efficient flood risk management scheme (3, 9)	a strategic and holistic approach that recognises the complexity of the system and accommodates the diverse range of uses and users is needed for planning, flood management and conservation objectives (2, 4, 8, 9)		flooding risk management is continuing issue in the UK taking quite a lot of resources (EA level of resources needed compared to 10 years earlier) (8, 9)
	housing crisis (availability of houses) (1, 4, 6, 7, 8)	samples to measure carbon sequestration (2, 5, 7)	pressure on the habitat due to maintenance and management activities (e.g. heavy trucks) (3, 5)	managed realignment is not perceived as effective in the current state (2, 3, 6)	wildlife disturbance (1, 3, 5)	net zero and carbon credits (1, 8)		housing crisis (availability of houses) (2, 3, 9)
	net gain, net zero policies and carbon credits (1, 4, 5, 8, 9)		wildlife disturbance (2, 4)	responsibilities are fragmented and not always clear (1, 2, 3, 4, 8)		switch from a sector/field-based approach to a system-based approach (2, 4, 5, 7, 8, 9)		net gain, net zero policies and carbon credits (2, 3, 5, 8, 9)
	post Brexit and Covid extremely challenging economic environment for the UK (5, 6, 7)			siltation of outfalls (1, 2, 3, 4, 5, 6, 8, 9)				the need for biodiversity protection was ongoing and wider benefits of biodiversity and functioning being recognised (5, 8)
	responsibilities are fragmented and not always clear (5, 9)							
	RSPB overall strategy/goal (2, 3, 4, 5, 7, 8, 9)							
	the need for biodiversity protection was ongoing and wider benefits of biodiversity and functioning being recognised (7, 8)							

Table A3. Different themes within groups for each component. The numbers in brackets indicate the number of the group(s) that reported the entry. To analyse the DPSIR framework, we grouped similar entries into themes.

Social Acceptance	Drivers	Activities	Pressures	State	Impact	Responses	Preparatory Measures	Worldview
desire to support natural habitat and biodiversity (6)	Brexit workforce reduced (6)	changing values and attitudes (mindsets) (3)	biodiversity and pressures on the habitat (2, 3, 5)	flooding risk management and general maintenance (1, 2, 5)	changing values and attitudes (6)	changing values and attitudes (5)	accessibility of knowledge (7)	austerity & lack of funding (5)
different vocabularies and knowledge about Nature-based Solutions (1, 3)	climate change and local impacts (1, 2, 4, 7, 9)	climate change and biodiversity crisis (3)	changing agricultural practices (1)	food (in)security and farming (2, 6, 7)	climate change and biodiversity crises (6)	community engagement and awareness (1, 3, 5)	develop a strategic solution for farming and food supply (2)	biodiversity crises (2, 4, 8, 9)
displacement (7)	creation of Internal Drainage Board (IDB) (7)	communities' engagement (3, 5)	climate change (1)	human developments and natural processes (1, 4, 8, 9)	competing interests (7)	farming recognition and future (2, 3, 6, 7)	increase of trust and procedural justice (8)	changing values and attitudes (1, 4)
effects on local prosperity (3)	flood risk management strategies and increased cost in the UK in the last 10 years (3, 5, 7)	flood risk management (4)	climate change (1)	negative perception of farmers changes to livelihood and local economy (3)	decrease in trust in risk management authorities (4, 6)	increased funding for local government and maintenance (1, 5)	innovative approaches to farming and water management that work with nature (e.g. wetland creation for water storage that would also increase biodiversity, paludiculture with lowland peat) (5, 8, 9)	climate change (2, 3, 8)
increased perception and/or experience of flooding (5, 9)	food security and Government policies (6, 7)	food imports (6)	decrease in trust in risk management authorities (8)	perception that sea level rise (SLR) is not a problem in the Northwest (4)	economy and prices (5, 7)	need for policy changes (1, 6, 7)	innovative approaches to farming and water management that work with nature (e.g. wetland creation for water storage that would also increase biodiversity, paludiculture with lowland peat) (5, 8, 9)	decrease in trust in risk management authorities (8)
lack of willingness to engage due to past experience (7)	funding (2, 3, 5)	funding partnerships (3)	flooding issues and costs (5, 8)	wildlife and conservation of habitat (6, 9)	farming and food security (5, 6)	research about carbon sequestration (8)	investigate financial benefits of carbon vs farming (6)	funding priorities not in line with nature-based solutions (9)
managed realignment is not perceived as an efficient flood risk management scheme in the current state (5, 8)	Income generation (3)	housing development (1, 5, 6)	funding and economic challenges (e.g. post Brexit) (3, 6, 8)		flooding risk management and flooding events (1, 5, 7)		more funding for flood prevention and wastewater treatment (2, 5, 7)	geo-political priorities (5, 7)
management issues (5, 9)	interest on carbon sequestration (1)	management and maintenance (2, 4, 9)	housing crisis (availability of houses) (5)		Infrastructural issues (1, 3, 5)		more research about the effectiveness of MR, sources of flooding, carbon sequestration and carbon markets (4, 7)	housing crisis (5)
political benefit or cost (3)	politics (3, 7)	net zero and carbon credits (7)	human activities (e.g. farming, agriculture, etc) and land use change (3, 5, 6)		sea-level rise (7)		need for a more co-ordinated, inclusive and strategic planning and governance (2, 3, 5, 6, 7, 8, 9)	managed realignment is not perceived as an efficient flood risk management scheme (7)
the understanding of ecosystem services and intertidal habitats and processes is widely understood (8)	population and housing (1, 6)	pressure on the habitat and wildlife (7)	increased pressure on the drainage system (4, 5)		wildlife, biodiversity and coastal habitat (1, 3, 8)		need for clarity about responsibilities and future strategies (3, 6)	need for more effective engagement of communities in the decision-making process (9)
trust (1, 4, 5)	pressure on the habitat (8)	RSPB overall strategy/goal (5)	internal tourism (3)				need for communities' engagement, local knowledge and increased awareness (5, 9)	post Brexit and Covid extremely challenging economic environment for the UK (4, 9)
			responsibilities are fragmented and not always clear (6)				social acceptance (7)	the understanding of ecosystem services and intertidal habitats and processes is widely understood (5)
			siltation of outfalls (7)				wellbeing - mental health - encourage people to use existing paths (3)	

Table A4. Final shared framework created by participants. The entries are reported here as they were indicated by participants.

Social Acceptance	Drivers	Activities	Pressures	State	Impacts	Responses	Preparatory Measures	Worldview
changing values and attitudes	cheap food Government policy	education/increased awareness	increased pressure on the drainage system due to the housing development that leads to over flow/over capacity of the system	changes in estuarine dynamics	competing interests	"Farming with nature" finding innovative ways of farming with water (e.g. paludiculture with lowland peat)	accessibility of knowledge	carbon issues and interest on carbon sequestration
displacement	climate change and biodiversity crises	engagement, getting people on board	limited and/or lack funding	decrease in trust in risk management authorities	flooding of farmlands	catchment view rather than coast, defence, farmland. Need holistic view	active engagement with communities. Produces the feeling of "ownership"	climate change and biodiversity crises
lack of willingness to engage due to past experience	funding partnerships	funding partnerships	the need for biodiversity protection was on going and wider benefits of biodiversity and functioning being recognised	flooding risk management is a continuing issue in the UK taking quite a lot of resources (EA level of resources needed compared to 10 years earlier)	incoherence (Impacts + State)	education/increased awareness	better cooperation	food security and cheap food policies, housing instead of food production
low levels of trust	house development	house development near the Douglas river	wildlife disturbance	food (in) security	increase in house prices and insurance	incentives for farmers and landowners (ELMs, LNRS)	better evidence on blue carbon, and carbon markets	geo-politics and priorities
managed realignment is not perceived as an efficient flood risk management scheme	increasing of rainfall	management and maintenance of the realigned site, outfalls, main rivers & watercourses		impact on food security	increased flood experience	more opportunities for communication across interest groups and organisations	changes in funding rules for flood management	managed realignment is not perceived as effective in the current state
terms like "Nature-based solutions" not well known by much of public	local importance of climate change (SLR, temp, pH, salt,...)	mindsets		incoherence (Impacts + State)	managed realignment is not perceived as an efficient flood risk management scheme	need for transformations	creational of Internal Drainage Board (IDB)	nobody listens
	misunderstandings and misconceptions around NbS. Seen as sub-standard	what activities are RSPB doing that influence the state now? (if any)		increased flood experience	sea level rise	RECOGNISE farming's contribution to the local economy	develop a Strategic Solution to ensure Hesketh Bank farmland can continue to grow food for the County	that communities should be involved in a meaningful way in decision-making
	net gain and net zero policies + climate change and biodiversity crises			increased flood risk - particularly surface water	surface water flooding e.g. the Dib rd, shore road, Hesketh Bank	recognise the Grade 1 food producing land	expertise of practitioners: i) upskilling, ii) Nbs, iii) deliberative processes	the need for biodiversity protection was on going and wider benefits of biodiversity and functioning being recognised (recognised but not a priority for individuals)
	net Zero and carbon credits			lack of maintenance		resourcing of local government	good governance	way that funding works disconnected from nature-based solutions need/drive
	other flood risk strategies (FRMP, SMP)			levels of land falling below saltmarsh due to accretion and changes in drainage		TRANSITIONAL too many barriers between different systems - natural processes	invest in flood prevention: i) from the sea, ii) fluvial and runoff. Invest in waste water treatment	
	politics			managed realignment is not perceived as effective in the current state		wetland creation for water management + storage + wildlife habitat	more coordinated Strategic planning and joint working from: i) Statutory Authorities, ii) Charities/pressure groups, iii) Landowners	

Table A4. Final shared framework created by participants. The entries are reported here as they were indicated by participants. Continuation.

Social Acceptance	Drivers	Activities	Pressures	State	Impacts	Responses	Preparatory Measures	Worldview
	politics			managed realignment is not perceived as effective in the current state		wetland creation for water management + storage + wildlife habitat	more co-ordinated Strategic planning and joint working from: i) Statutory Authorities, ii) Charities/pressure groups, iii) Landowners	
	protecting people and properties			perception that sea level rise is less a problem in the NW. Isostatic shift no longer keeping up with sea level rise so it is an issue.			more scientific evidence into the effectiveness of managed realignment	
	responsibilities are fragmented and not always clear			responsibilities are fragmented and not always clear			more stewardship needed enabling communities to have a stake. Needs a system for incorporating national priorities as well as local needs + is responsive.	
	restriction of the flow width of the River Ribble			sewage discharge			need a big picture planning system for land-use maximising benefits in a sustainable way.	
	RSPB overall strategy/goal						need meaningful engagement NOT public consultations	
	sea level rise (---> water table)						new forms of Institutional more pragmatic approaches	
	sea level rise, creation of Internal Drainage Board (IDB), food security						other new nature markets?	
				siltation of outfalls + quality of infrastructures			overcoming entrenched views	
				wicked problem			raise coastal management + flood management up in the policy agenda	
				wildlife associated with marshes increased relative to pre-intervention?			separate study on surface water flooding and drainage	
							social acceptance and debate needed	
							supporting key decision makers including MPs into a deeper understanding of the issues and complexities	
							testing and trialing new methods for taking water off the land. Wind pumps, storage tanks through outfalls	